

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS PATANJALI PRODUCTS – WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ERODE CITY

G. Gurusanthosini* & G. Gomathi**

Assistant Professor, Department of Corporate Secretaryship With CA and Professional Accounting, Kongu Arts and Science College, (Autonomous), Erode, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: G. Gurusanthosini & G. Gomathi, “A Study on Consumer Preference towards Patanjali Products – With Special Reference to Erode City”, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 163-166, 2017.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2017 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) are products that are sold quickly and at relatively low cost. A marketing concept that encompasses a customer's impression, awareness and consciousness about a company or its offerings. Customer perception is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experiences and other channels. Patanjali is one of the great competitors of FMCG products in the market. So this study is carried out to know why customers are interested to purchase the Patanjali products. An Indian FMCG started in 2008 by Baba Ramdev and Acharya Balkrishna. This company has claimed a revenue of Rs 5000crore, the company is expected to clock revenues of Rs.20,000crore by fiscal year 2020(IIFL Institutional Equities report). This study also aims at identifying customer's preference towards Patanjali products with special reference to Erode District people.

Key Words: FMCG, Customer Preference, Competitor & Patanjali Product

1. Introduction:

The growing demand for herbal therapy to lead a healthy life has prompted Yoga-Guru Ramdev to map the portfolio of true needs of modern Indian which goes beyond food, clothing and shelter but strives for a healthy life style. Accordingly he engineered his offerings in tune with the needs of all under the brand Patanjali Ayurved through his expertise on the art of content marketing and mass customization. From March 2012, Patanjali brand marked its entry into the herbal retail market and FMCG with 'Swadeshi' flavour of products ranging from body care, healthcare, home care, digestive, cosmetics, toiletries etc. Patanjali Ayurved Limited is a Haridwar based Indian FMCG company with a market valuation of close to USD 2 billion (Rs 13,000 cr). It has become the fastest growing Indian FMCG organization till date and its growth rate on revenue has created high benchmarks for competition to emulate. The following figure narrates the story of Patanjali Ayurved's phenomenal growth:

2. Objectives:

- ✓ To study the influence of various factor on the purchase of Patanjali products like price, quality and Brand Awareness.
- ✓ To know the source of consumer preference
- ✓ To examine purchasing behavior of the consumer gender wise and age wise.
- ✓ To study the satisfaction level of consumers after using 'Patanjali' Products.
- ✓ To know why consumers are attached with Patanjali products

3. Research Methodology:

This paper is based on primary data collected through questionnaires from 50 users of Patanjali Products within Erode City. The questionnaire design is built up to know the type of products people use, the reason for their buying such product and their post buying satisfaction level from that product. Secondary sources have been used to collect information about 'Patanjali' brands. Journals, articles, research reports and government documents were reviewed to get the insight of the previous interventions that the stakeholders and policy makers have already in place. A Study on 'Patanjali' has ever changing marketing scenario over the globe has amplified the role of brand at unparalleled level. Every person is a consumer of different brands at the

same time. For analyzing the data and providing the relative of the research outcome suitable statistical techniques were applied.

4. Data Analysis:

Table 1: Demographic and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Consumers

Age Intervals	No. of Respondents	Percentage
15-25	5	10%
26-35	11	22%
36-45	20	40%
46-55	5	10%
Above 55	9	18%
Total	50 Respondents	100%
Gender	No. of Respondents	
Male	18	36%
Female	32	64%
Total	50 Respondents	100%
Marital Status	No. of Respondents	
Married	36	72%
Unmarried	14	28%
Total	50 Respondents	100%
Educational Status	No. of Respondents	
Illiterate	6	12%
School Level	11	22%
Degree / Diploma	20	40%
Professional	13	26%
Total	50 Respondents	100%
Occupation	No. of Respondents	
Employee	7	14%
Business	11	22%
Agriculture	10	20%
House Wives	17	34%
Others	5	10%
Total	50 Respondents	100%
Income Level	No. of Respondents	
Less Than 10,000	5	10%
10,001 to 20,000	13	26%
20,001 to 30,000	15	30%
More than 30,000	17	34%
Total	50 Respondents	100%

(Source questionnaire)

The above table depicts that total numbers of 50 respondents involved in this study, regarding demographic characteristics of the respondents, while considering the age group, 40% of the respondents were in the age group of 36-45 years. 64% were females the remaining 36% were males. Based on the findings, the respondents are mostly married persons with 72%, and 40% of the respondents are mostly Degree /Diploma holders, Finally, regarding the income level, 34% of the respondents were in the category of more than Rs. 30,000

Table 2: Consumer Preferences on Patanjali Products

Awareness of Varieties	No. of Respondents
Yes	26 (52%)
No	24(48%)
Total	50 (100%)
Sources of Awareness of the Product	No. of Respondents
TV	12 (24%)
Radio	11 (22%)
Friends	14(28%)
Neighbours	8(16%)
Relatives	3(6%)
Newspapers	2(4%)
Total	50 (100%)

Factors	No. of Respondents
Offers	2(4%)
Varieties	24(48%)
Price	14(28%)
Quality	6(12%)
Herbal	4(8%)
Total	50 (100%)
Most Preferred Products	No. of Respondents
Cosmetics	9(18%)
Food	6(12%)
Health Care	16(32%)
Detergents	17(34%)
Cloths	2(4%)
Total	50 (100%)
Expenditure Amount Expended	No. of Respondents
Less Than Rs. 500	19(38%)
Rs 500 To Rs. 1,000	19(38%)
Rs 1,001 To Rs. 2,000	10(20%)
Above 2,000	2(4%)
Total	50 (100%)
Level of Satisfaction	No. of Respondents
Highly Satisfied	33(66%)
Satisfied	12(24%)
Neutral	3(6%)
Dissatisfied	1(2%)
Highly Dissatisfied	0(0%)
Total	50 (100%)
Problems Faced While Purchasing Patanjali Products	No. of Respondents
Non Availability of Products in Retail Shops	29(58%)
Lack of Sufficient Stock	10(20%)
High Cost	0(0%)
Only Few Varieties	0(0%)
Non Availability of All Products in Online	6(12%)
Lack of Knowledge of the Product	5(10%)
Total	50 (100%)

(Source Questionnaire)

It is inferred from the above table 2 shows that 52% of the people are having awareness about the varieties in product. The respondents got more awareness about this product through their friends followed by Television. Most of the peoples prefer Patanjali because of huge varieties and quality. 34% of the respondents prefer the Detergents of Patanjali followed by HealthCare products. 38% of the respondents expended a minimum of Rs. 1,000 pm to purchase Patanjali product. The consumers of Patanjali are mostly highly satisfied due to the herbal ingredients in the products. 58% of the respondents are faced the problems like non-availability of products in retail shops and none of them insisted the problems like few varieties, high cost.

Table 3: Reason for Procuring Patanjali Products

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Ranking
Swedeshi	20(40%)	10(20%)	10(20%)	9(18%)	1(2%)	50(100%)	4
Availability at both online and offline	7(14%)	8(16%)	8(16%)	16(32%)	11(22%)	50(100%)	7
Hygenic and standard quality	28(56%)	9(18%)	5(10%)	5(10%)	3(6%)	50(100%)	1
Available at nearest retail shop	10(20%)	7(14%)	9(18%)	13(26%)	11(22%)	50(100%)	6
Promotional level was good	19(38%)	12(24%)	11(22%)	3(6%)	5(10%)	50(100%)	5
Available at reasonable price	26(52%)	14(28%)	7(14%)	2(4%)	1(2%)	50(100%)	2

Ayurvedic product	22(44%)	12(24%)	5(10%)	6(12%)	5(10%)	50(100%)	3
-------------------	---------	---------	--------	--------	--------	----------	---

(Source Questionnaire)

The above table states that 56% of respondents are purchasing this product because it is available at more hygienic and standard quality. Availability of products at reasonable price is one of the main factors for 52% of the respondents to purchase the product. The 44% of the respondents are preferring this product due to the ayurvedic ingredients in the product, 40% of the respondents are strongly agree that the Patanjali product are Indian product, so they prefer to purchase more than other FMCG products. But the 14% respondent has said the availability of products was less while compare to other products.

5. Suggestions:

- ✓ The samples should be distributed to the people.
- ✓ The product needs more promotional activities.
- ✓ The package of the product should be more attractive to increase the sales
- ✓ It should be easily available in retail stores.
- ✓ Offers & discounts should be announced frequently.

6. Conclusion:

Ayurvedic and Herbal remedies are available in all Patanjali and organic stores. Ayurvedic products are reasonably cost effective and well accepted by customers. They are easily available and do not have side effects. With its rich biodiversity and rich heritage of Indian medicinal system, India would draw world attention as an abode of eco-friendly medicinal systems that are in harmony with the nature, it is concluded that all the customers are aware of the product, and he customers are satisfied with the quality and price of the products. The Findings in the paper show that there are many significant factors that together make up the buying decision of the product. Patanjali is enjoying the advantageous position in market through spirituality element involved in its products. However, it should not ignore the competitors like Naturals, pure roots, Vindhya herbals. In this paper the findings shows Patanjali in order to retain more customers and satisfy them, must fulfill the claims made by the company before any other brand may mushroom up and take away the benefits of marketing through spirituality

7. References:

1. <http://www.allayurveda.com/discover.asp>
2. <https://www.inlifehealthcare.com/blog/benefits-ofayurveda-remedies/#.V66OcNR94ri>
3. http://www.ayurvedicbazaar.com/ayurvedic_books.php
4. <http://sublimemagazine.com/health-beauty/why-useherbal-medicine>
5. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Patanjali_Ayurved